

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES IN THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a socio-philosophical analysis of the interrelationship between national and universal values in the formation of a healthy lifestyle among young people. The study explores how moral, cultural, and social factors influence youth behavior and contribute to shaping their worldview in the context of globalization. The role of family, education, and social institutions in strengthening health culture and moral consciousness is examined. It is argued that harmonizing national traditions with universal human values ensures the development of both physical and spiritual health among youth. The article also proposes conceptual approaches and practical recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of educational and ideological activities aimed at forming a healthy and value-based lifestyle among the younger generation.

Entrance

It is impossible to imagine the national values of each nation without its history, spirituality, culture, unique customs, and traditions. "By value, we should understand the totality of the benefits and phenomena of nature and society, significant for a person and humanity, serving the interests and goals of nations, nationalities, and social groups, and being evaluated and valued by them. It is known that values are diverse in their essence. Among them, natural, material, spiritual, socio-political, and moral values stand out. Nevertheless, the highest value is the human being, life, rights and freedoms, a healthy and prosperous life. Honoring human dignity and honor is an important factor in the purification and prosperity of our society.

The "Action Strategy" being implemented in our country is a new stage of reforms, in which spiritual, social, and economic support for the population and families occupies a leading place. At the same time, based on economic and socio-political values, work has been established to listen to the concerns of the people, to ease their burdens, and to provide material and moral support to employees of state bodies. In one of his articles devoted to national traditions, Gulyamkhan Gafurov mentions the following manifestations of national values:

- 1) natural values;
- 2) economic values;

- 3) socio-political values;
- 4) spiritual values;
- 5) moral values.

Person, life, rights and freedoms, in particular, "Our ancestors, along with teaching knowledge, instilled in our children national-spiritual and moral values passed down from generation to generation." "Most Uzbeks prioritize caring for the well-being of their loved ones and neighbors. And this is the highest spiritual value, the pearl of the human soul"; "Economic value is a concept that means the consideration of mutual interests between individuals in the process of economic relations, the observance of such qualities as honesty, purity, tolerance, reliability." If we take the value of neighborliness as an example, then mutual trust between neighbors, receiving news, and providing material assistance are put to the forefront as national values. Spiritual heritage, cultural values, and ancient historical monuments are cited as the most important factors of life values.

The essence and significance of each value contribute to understanding the phenomena of nature, society, and the spiritual world, scientific generalization, and social and spiritual development. Along with recent achievements in the field of upbringing, the priority of national and universal values and traditions has been achieved in the family, schools, and public organizations. The words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society to ensure that our youth develop independently thinking, possess high intellectual and spiritual potential, are individuals who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale, and are happy," inspire us all to raise the younger generation as mature and well-rounded individuals based on national values. In his treatise "Issues of Independence and Upbringing," Safo Ochil writes: "National values include traditions passed down to us from our ancestors: Eid al-Fitr, Eid al-Adha, Navruz, grain sowing and harvest festivals, cradle ceremonies, circumcision ceremonies, weddings related to sons and daughters, housewarming ceremonies, various funeral ceremonies, as well as various folk traditions - hashar, respect for parents, honor for youth, kindness to the elderly, adherence to national etiquette and moral standards, pursuing knowledge, achieving family stability, appreciating teachers, visiting the graves of the deceased, love for the people, loving and cherishing the Homeland, voluntary military service, being an internationalist, gentleness and eloquence, and the beauty of human behavior, generosity, nobility, loyalty to promises, imagination, knowledge acquisition, wisdom, tolerance, politeness, cleanliness and purity, purity of heart, politeness, and similar human qualities.

Spiritual values, in a broad sense, are manifested in all human actions, activities, behavior, manners, relationships with people, in a narrow sense - in the philosophical, religious, political, moral, legal views, thinking, worldview of people. In today's era of the development of innovative technologies, only a truly spiritual and enlightened person knows the value of a person, understands their national values, national identity, lives in a free and independent society, for each person to be able to fight selflessly for our independent state to take its rightful place in the world community, a person determines self-awareness, intelligence, the ability to distinguish good from ignorance, justice from vigilance from indifference, wisdom from ignorance.

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